

A Study of Anaemia in Paediatric Patients in A Tertiary Care Hospital at Rajkot (Gujarat), India: One year study**Raghunath Baria¹, Amit Agravat ², Gauravi Dhruva³, Krupal Pujara⁴**¹2nd Year Resident, Department of Pathology, PDU Medical College and Hospital, Rajkot, India²Professor, Department of Pathology, PDU Medical College and Hospital, Rajkot, India³Professor and Head, Department of Pathology, PDU Medical College and Hospital, Rajkot, India⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, PDU Medical College and Hospital, Rajkot, India

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Abstract:**Background:** Anemia is one of the most common hematologic abnormalities found in newborns and children. It leads to increased morbidity and mortality, neurologic complications, risk of low birth weight, infection, and heart failure. While approaching a child having anemia, detailed history, particularly diet, environmental factors are helpful leading to diagnosis.**Aims and Objectives:** The present study was undertaken to describe etiological factors, age, sex, severity of anemia, for which study of anemia was done in "Central Clinical Laboratory (CCL), Department of Pathology, P.D.U Medical College & Hospital, Rajkot, Gujarat which is a tertiary care hospital in western India.**Materials and Methods:** A prospective study was conducted among 1348 pediatric patients who attended clinic one year between June 2023 to May 2024 in a tertiary care hospital at whose blood samples and socio-demographic information were collected. Hemoglobin, indices, WBC & RBC counts were counted using automated hematology cell counter. Grading was done by WHO criteria and morphology was studied by peripheral blood smear examination.**Result:** A high prevalence 463 (34.34%) of anemia was observed among 1348 pediatric patients commonly seen in age group (2-6 years) in which 775(57.50%) were males and 573 (42.50%) were females. According to blood indices and peripheral blood smear analysis hypochromic microcytic anemia 835(61.94%) was the commonest morphological type of anemia followed by normochromic normocytic anemia 375 (27.81%), dimorphic anemia 63(4.67 %), macrocytic anemia 48(3.56%), hemolytic anemia 27 (2.0%).**Conclusion:** Hypochromic microcytic anemia was found to be the most common cause of anemia in pediatric patients this study. Identifying of etiologies of anemia can be helpful in defining diagnostic and therapeutic strategies, which contributes toward the better management of patients.**Keywords:** Anemia, Children, Hypochromic Microcytic Anemia.

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Introduction

Anemia is characterized by decreased number of circulating red blood cells or functionally as a condition where numbers of erythrocytes are not sufficient to meet metabolic demands. According to WHO roughly a quarter of the world's population suffers from anemia, including almost half of preschool-age children. Iron deficiency anemia being the most common cause of anemia worldwide, other causes are hemoglobinopathies, infection, and chronic diseases. The increasing availability of genetic testing is providing new mechanistic insights into inherited anemia and allowing diagnosis in many previously undiagnosed cases.

Materials and Methods: The present study was carried out in the Central Clinical Laboratory

(CCL), Department of Pathology, P.D.U. Medical College and Hospital, Rajkot, Gujarat carried out over a period of 1 year between June 2023 to May 2024 which is a tertiary care hospital in western India.

Sample Size: A prospective study of 1348 pediatric patients who attending clinic in a tertiary care hospital.**Inclusion Criteria:** Pediatric patients age <18 year who were indoor admitted patients in our institute.**Exclusion Criteria:** Diagnosed cases of anemia on treatment, history of recent blood transfusion. The clinical details were obtained from CCL requisition forms accompanying the blood samples. The

detailed history, clinical and physical examination and hematological investigations were performed. Blood counts were performed on a 5part BC-6200 - Automated Hematology cell counter which was followed by peripheral smear examination. Differential count and red cell morphology were done manually by staining the blood smears with Field's and Leishman's stain. Following Investigations were carried out: Hemoglobin, RBC count, WBC count, Platelet count, Hematocrit, Red cell indices, RDW and Peripheral blood smear examination.

Results

Total number of pediatric samples were 2000 (100%) out of which 1348 (67.4%) were having anemia.

Out of these patients, 775(57.50%) were males and 573 (42.50%) were females, having male: female ratio of 1.3:1. The age of these patients was <18 years.

Table 1: Definitions of anemia

Population	Hemoglobin Gm /Dl
Infants	11
Children aged 6 months to <5 years	11
Children aged 5 to <12 years	11.5
Children aged 12 to <15 years	12

Figure 1: Age distribution of patients

Out of total 1348 pediatric patients most common affected age group was 2-6 years in 463 (34.34%) anemic patients followed by age group 6 month-2 year 375 patients (26.48%), 6 year – 12 year 291 patients (21.58%), 0-6 month 112 patients (9.67%), 12 – 18 year 107 patients (7.93%).

Figure 2: Classification of anemia according to severity

According to this table the most common anemia was moderate anemia 711 patients (52.8%) followed by mild anemia 405 patients (30%), severe anemia 232 patients (17.2%).

Table 2: Red cell morphology on peripheral blood smear of anemia

RBC Morphology On Peripheral Blood Smear	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
Normocytic Normochromic anemia	375	27.81
Microcytic Hypochromic anemia	835	61.94
Macrocytic anemia	48	3.56
Dimorphic anemia	63	4.67
Haemolytic anemia	27	2.02
Total case of anemia	1348	100

Out of total 1348 pediatric patients peripheral blood smear analysis hypochromic microcytic anemia 835(61.94%) was the commonest morphological type of anemia followed by normochromic normocytic anemia 375 (27.81 %), dimorphic anemia 63(4.67 %), macrocytic anemia 48(3.56%), haemolytic anemia 27 (2.0 %).

Figure 3: Peripheral smear showing Microcytic Hypochromic Anemia

Figure 4: Peripheral smear showing Dimorphic anemia, morphologically characterized by two cell population

Figure 5: Peripheral smear showing haemolytic anemia. Morphologically characterized by Reticulocytes, Polychromatic, polychromatophilic red blood cell

Figure 6: Peripheral smear showing macrocytic anemia with hyper segmented neutrophils with macro-ovalocyte

Figure 7: Hemolytic anemia further work up

HPLC (High performance liquid chromatography) was done for further work up of haemolytic anemia. Out of 27 (100%) patients 16 (59.25%) were of thalassemia, 9 (33.33%) patients were of sickle cell anemia and 2 (7.4%) patients were of auto immune hemolytic anemia.

F Concentration = 34.0* %
 A2 Concentration = 57.4* %
 *Values outside of expected ranges
 Analysis comments:

Figure 8: HPLC reports of thalassemia major patient which showing increase level of HbA2 concentration: 57.4%, Hb f concentration 34.0 %

Figure 9: Prevalence of iron deficiency anemia

There were total 835(100%) patients of hypochromic microcytic anemia. Out of those 724 (86.70%) patient’s serum ferritin level was less than 15, total iron binding capacity >300 and transferrin saturation level was less than 10 which is suggesting of iron deficiency anemia. 111(13.3%) patient’s serum ferritin level > 15, total iron binding capacity < 360 and transferrin saturation level >10 which is suggesting of anemia due to chronic disease.

Micronutrient deficiencies were constructed as binary variables following sex- and age-specific WHO cutoffs (Benoist, [7]; Namaste et al., [6]; WHO, [8,9]): iron deficiency as ferritin < 15 ng/ml. Iron-deficiency anaemia (IDA) is a common clinical problem throughout the world and an enormous public health problem in developing

countries. The cornerstone of the laboratory identification of IDA is a low haemoglobin and serum ferritin concentration although a normal serum ferritin does exclude IDA. When the serum ferritin is normal in an anaemic patient with iron-deficient erythropoiesis, it is common practise to perform a bone marrow examination to diagnose IDA.

The recent introduction of serum transferrin receptor measurements is a useful alternative for distinguishing IDA from the anaemia of chronic disease because the serum receptor concentration is usually elevated in patients with IDA but normal in patients with anaemia due to inflammation or neoplasia. It is helpful for the clinician to be aware of the causes of physiological IDA.

Figure 10: Bone marrow examination

According to this table in our study 48 (100%) patients were of macrocytic anemia.

Out of 48 patients bone marrow examination was done in 22 patients.

Out of those 14 patients were a nutritional anemia predominantly megaloblastic anemia and 8 patients were dimorphic anemia predominantly megaloblastic anemia.

Prevalence of anemia in our study was 67.4% which is in accordance with study conducted by Venkatesh G [1] at Ahmedabad in which prevalence was 81.2% respectively, Shally Awasthi et al [2] found prevalence of 37 to 38% in studies done in Uttar Pradesh, Bijan Keikhaei [3] found prevalence of 43.9% among children of South West Iran, Peter R Dallman [4] found prevalence of 6% in United States of America.

Discussion

Table 3: Global distribution of anemia in study

Global Distribution	Prevalence Of Anemia (%)
Our Study(Rajkot-Gujarat) [2024]	67.4
Gujarat(Ahmedabad) [2013][1]	81.20
Tamilnadu [2008] [7]	52.88
Assam [2018] [10]	32.00
South East Asia [2007][3]	85.10
America [1980][4]	76.70
Egypt [2018][11]	27.2
Congo [2016][11]	66.6

Prevalence of anemia according to different age group in our study show prevalence of anemia is highest in the age group between 1 to 2 years which is 33% and it is highest as compared to other age groups in accordance with studies of Shally Avasthi et al [2] and Bijan keikhaei [3].

The most common reason behind this is continued breast feeding beyond 6 month and improper complimentary feeding which leads to deficiency of iron because breast milk is deficient in iron. Improper complimentary feeding techniques lead to various types of infection and malnutrition.

Hypochromic microcytic anemia is the most common type of anemia followed by dimorphic,

macroovalocytic, and hemolytic which is in accordance with previous studies like Shally Awasthi [2] and Venkatesh G [1]. Iron deficiency anemia is the most common cause for hypochromic microcytic anemia. Sex wise distribution of anemia shows that hypochromic microcytic anemia is more prevalent in female whereas there is no such sex wise difference seen in case of macroovalocytic and dimorphic anemia as well as hemolytic anemia which is in accordance with studies of Neeraj Jain et al [5].

Conclusion

From our study which includes pediatric patients till 12 years age group and both the sexes; we came

to know that anemia is more prevalent in the age group of 1 to 2 years and most common morphological types are hypochromic microcytic anemia followed by dimorphic anaemia respectively. The most common reason behind both morphological types is nutritional deficiency most common of iron, vitamin B12 and folic acid.

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